

The Extent of Achieving Webb's Depth of Knowledge (DOK) in the United Arab Emirates' Grades 6 - 11 Final Exams' Questions

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Article Info	Abstract
Article History	<i>The study's importance lies in investigating the extent to which the final achievement exams in the United Arab Emirates achieve the depth of knowledge levels (DOK). It also lies in providing adequate information as feedback for supervisors (Exams and Assessment Specialists) in the Exams and Assessments Directorate in the Ministry of Education about their questions' nature; this helps them review the method and style of writing questions. This study aims to determine the extent of Webb's Depth of Knowledge (DOK) levels in the core subject of the questions in "final exams" of Grades 6 – 11 students in the Ministry of Education in the United Arab Emirates. The study groups and the actual samples of all final exam questions for basic materials (Islamic Education, Arabic, English, mathematics, science) established by the Assessment Department at the Ministry of Education for the first semester of 2015/2016 of (30) exams.</i>
Received: November 29, 2020	<i>The researcher used the descriptive approach manner in this study in an analytical style. To verify that study questions are statistically computerized, a statistical packages program has been used in the Social Sciences (SPSS). The following statistical treatments and descriptive and analytical have been used: arithmetic means, standard deviations, and percentages, and analysis of variance, (One -Way ANOVA), and (LSD) test comparisons posterior, (T-test), and the results of the study: The general level of cognitive depth skills for grades 6th, 7th, 9th, 10th, and 11th (Islamic education, Arabic, English, mathematics, science) was remembering, while the lowest cognitive depth skills were for extended thinking. The objective exams have achieved the depth of knowledge in all its dimensions compared to the editorial questions, and that there are virtual differences in the dimensions of the depth of knowledge (memory, concepts, and skills, strategic thinking, extended thinking), depending on the variable type of material in favor of Islamic education and science. Differences were only significant in the areas of strategic and extended thinking. The differences in terms of concepts and skills were between grades (6th, 7th, and 8th) on the one hand, and 11th grade on the other hand, where the differences were in favor of the eleventh grade, and differences in thinking ranged between grades (sixth, eighth and ninth) On the other hand, the differences were in favor of the eleventh grade.</i>
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1. Introduction

The evaluation process for any educational program involves making decisions affecting directly or indirectly the learner. Such findings imply continuing a particular academic program or thoroughly reviewing and replacing it based on how effective the program is in facilitating the learning process, or the extent of its effectiveness in bringing about learner's progress towards achieving the already prepared desirable goals, and in all aspects of the physical, mental and emotional growth. It is also likely to find that the evaluation process's information had come in one way or another from the learner and the classroom in particular. Since the accuracy of the decision depends on the accuracy of the available information, accessing reliable and valid data is the cornerstone of the evaluation process. The student's evaluation is the cornerstone of the integrated construction of the evaluation process.

It is well known that no type of test can cover all the subject matter students learn in a particular area. Therefore, it is in its best form a sample of the desired achievement behavior. For the results of such a test to be expressive and reliable, its questions had better be highly representative of the content course. The exam building process should be based on the so-called specification table that links the desired objectives and the students' subject. In this way, the teacher has a full picture of the material taught and the goals targeted through the teaching process, thereby reducing each table cell's relative importance and its representation rate in the

sample questions. Therefore, if the teacher considers all that, he can choose a representative sample of the academic content in the light of the desired educational goals to write test questions (Kilani, lentils, met, 2003).

The teacher should be aware of a particular subject's goals at different levels and know how to plan to teach. The teacher who wants to succeed in teaching as a career has to develop his planning, implementation, and evaluation skills in the teaching process (2003Carnen & Carpenter).

Study problem and questions

This study's problem arises by identifying the extent to which questions of final exams in the United Arab Emirates achieve the levels of Depth of Knowledge (DOK) and find out the dominant and most common levels in these exams. It tries to answer the following questions:

Question 1:

What is the most common Depth of Knowledge level in Grades 6 -11 final examinations of core subjects (Islamic Education, Arabic, English, Mathematics, and Science)?

Question 2:

Are there any significant differences at the level of significance ($0.05 = \alpha$) between the Depth of Knowledge dominant levels in the core subjects (Islamic Education, Arabic, English, Mathematics, Science) in the question of final exams of Grades 6 – 11 students that attributes to question type (subjective and objective) variable?

Question 3:

Are there any significant differences at the level of significance ($0.05 = \alpha$) between the Depth of Knowledge dominant levels in the core subjects (Islamic Education, Arabic, English, Mathematics, Science) in the question of final exams of Grades 6 – 11 students that attribute to subject type variable?

Question 4:

Are there any significant differences at the level of significance ($0.05 = \alpha$) between the Depth of Knowledge dominant levels in the core subjects (Islamic Education, Arabic, English, Mathematics, Science) in the question of final exams of Grades 6 – 11 students that attribute to grade type variable?

Objectives of the study

This study aims to determine the extent of Webb's Depth of Knowledge (DOK) levels in the core subject of the questions in "final exams" of Grades 6 – 11 students in the Ministry of Education in the United Arab Emirates.

Importance of the Study

The study's importance lies in investigating the extent to which the final achievement exams in the United Arab Emirates achieve the depth of knowledge levels of (DOK) (Recall and Reproduction, Concepts and Skills, Strategic Thinking, Extended Thinking). In addition to shedding light on the evaluation, that would give an accurate idea about the set exams' nature and how far they achieve these levels. It also provides adequate information as feedback for supervisors (Exams and Assessment Specialists) in the Exams and Assessments Directorate in the Ministry of Education about their questions' nature. This helps them to review the method and style of writing questions. This study is expected to provide decision-makers in the Ministry of Education of the United Arab Emirates with accurate and realistic information on the status of exams set by supervisors and specialists in the Exams and Assessments Directorate, and this aims at developing the measurement and evaluation in the Ministry of Education, which leads to improving the educational process of teaching-learning outcomes.

Study terms and Procedural Definitions

Depth of Knowledge is a standards-based assessment developed by the scientist Norman Webb (1997). It includes all forms of knowledge, whether procedural or descriptive, mostly, and each process from simple to most structural complex. Web divided depth of knowledge into four levels: (Recall, Concepts, skills, strategic thinking, and extended thinking).

Theoretical framework

Tests are considered the most critical measurement tools that can be used to evaluate academic achievement for students to judge the level of achievement in the various courses. The theoretical tests are usually linked to teaching specific materials that have already been taught. So when we want to prepare a test, it must represent everything that matched students' and teachers' interests during this process or the training process on the practical aspects. One of the appropriate methods for this is to prepare a list of topics that have been taught (content analysis), and then we determine the relative weights of all essential and minor parts of the subject matter (Darwaza, 2000). The relative values of the topics should reflect the interest of the teacher.

Those tests' essential characteristics are the selection process of these tests based on the relative importance of each of the content topics and the type of objectives to be achieved. There are several features or specifications of objectives, and they must be realistic, applicable in the light of environmental conditions school mainstream desired by the students, and meet their needs and the needs of their community. That will fit these educational objectives with the general educational goals and be an extension and a complement. Those specifications can be considered an outline that includes headlines of the content of the subject matter and the percentage and the number of questions allocated to each part of that content (2002 Reinckens).

Many people view students' achievement traditionally. They believe that their achievement is related to some cognitive skills they acquire through learning prescribed textbooks. Within this narrow view, the exams become restricted to measure the students' abilities to retrieve scattered facts and information related to the content using simple question items.

These exams are generally built vaguely. i.e., without depending on a clear framework that gives meaning to the grades. That is why these question items do not make a clear and scientific-based exam paper, as they do not represent comprehensive knowledge and skills included in the target content. The answers do not require higher thinking skills like awareness of the relationships, giving alternatives, making decisions, and problem-solving that the learner might face in his daily life.

How can we benefit from the results of these achievement tests and rely upon in making good and precise decisions regarding the learner as a thinker and a creative person, the teacher as a designer and architect in education, and strategies of education as a methodology and scientific style and in the educational program as an interacting and renewable system? (Allam, Salah al 2011).

These narrow and limited views of the concept of academic achievement and educational philosophy are concerned with the differences between individuals and the balance between them, the consequent of the measuring methods, and the collection's evaluation focusing on what specific information a learner has kept in his mind, this does not fit future requirements for education and the need to change in this century, and that change is characterized by the explosion of knowledge, technological progress, and the revolution in information and communication.

Education will lead the change and play a key role in developing future communities we look for. The issues of vital educational and related problems are associated with the three reactants and their challenges. They are growing, maintaining, and protecting the environment and peace. That will become the focus of international and national policies. Also, the variables related to population growth, scientific and technological developments, and patterns of the jobs developed are expected to become one of the variables of education in the future (USIA, 1991).

Without attention to the learning process element, the learning process does not occur as it should, or its impact is weak. The questions vary in the variety of objectives and classification criteria; There are many views to classify questions such as Weaver and wesensi, Stal Wansallon, John Wilson, and Gilford's classification. (Al-Khatib al-Khatib, 1997; Zayton, 1997; Kitami, 1998; Marso & Moore , 1995 (Comme & Hubley, 2003; Pigge, 2002. They include.

First: questions according to Bloom's Taxonomy, where he classified his questions in the form of a pyramid. He viewed the items in any exam to be distributed into six cognitive levels. They are as follows:

A- Remembering: 45% of the total questions.

B- Understanding and comprehension:10% of the total questions.

C- Application: 20% of the total questions.

D- Analysis: 10% of the total questions.

E- Synthesis: 10% of the total questions.

F - Evaluation: 5% of the total questions.

Second: Norman Web's classification of the Depth-of-Knowledge

Norman (1997) developed the process and criteria for systematic analysis to align standards and standardized assessments. Since then, the process and the criteria shown in the review's application also show this curriculum alignment. This section presents a model of the depth of knowledge to analyze the cognitive expectations required of criteria and methodology activities and assessment tasks (B, 1997). This model is based on the assumption that all curriculum elements can be classified based on the cognitive demands required to produce an acceptable response.

Each set reflects a different level of expected cognitive tasks or the depth of knowledge requires to complete the task. It should be noted that the term knowledge, as it is used here, is intended to cover all forms of knowledge (procedural, declarative, etc.) substantially. Table 1 shows a modified version of the model.

Table (1) shows the percentage of questions for each level of depth of knowledge

Level	Depth of knowledge	percentage
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1	Remembering And Retrieval	65%
2	The skills and the Concepts	20%
3	Short - Term Strategic Thinking	10%
4	Extended Thinking	5%

Level 1 – Remembering and Retrieval

This level includes approaches that fall in this category of basic tasks that require students to remember or re-produce knowledge and skills elements. It usually involves the subject's content at this particular level to work with facts and terms and objects' properties. It can also include the use of procedures and simple formulas, a bit of the conversion, or the extended target of knowledge required to process tasks that fall into this category. Also, it includes keywords that often indicate this exceptional level: lists identify and define. A student who answers a single item under level one either knows the answer or not; this means that the answer does not need to "find" or "give a solution."

Level 2 - skills and concepts

Level 2 includes the involvement of some mental processes away from remembering or re-production of the answer. This generally requires students to compare or contrast people, places, events, and concepts. They should also convert information from one form to another, classify or sort items into meaningful categories, describe or explain issues and problems and patterns, cause and effect, the importance or impact, relationships, and views or operations. It requires going beyond description or interpretation of the recalled information to describe or explain "the result" or the "how" or "why." The learner must take advantage of the information in a different context from all that he learned.

This level also includes elements in the curricula that fall in this category to work with or apply the skills and/or concepts relevant to the field of study in a lab environment task. Usually, it involves the subject's content in this special level to work with a set of principles, categories, reasoning, and protocols. Besides, it requests students to convert target knowledge before answering. For example, the mental processes that often indicate this special level are as follows: summarize, estimate, organize, classify, and infer.

Level 3 - Short-term strategic thinking

The question items that fall into this category require using short-term operations of the higher-order thinking, such as analysis and evaluation, to solve the real problems with predictable results. It gives the reasoning the main mark on this level. Also, the expectation given tends to involve coordination between applying knowledge and skill in many subject areas to carry out operations and reach a solution based on the project. The key processes that often indicate this particular level are as follows: analysis, interpretation, and support with evidence, and dissemination of and innovation.

Level 4 - Expanded strategic thinking

At this level, the curriculum elements require the extended operations of higher-order thinking such as synthesizing, reasoning, evaluating, and modifying plans over time. Students who participate in the conduct of investigations to solve real problems with unexpected results and utilize and sustainability of strategic thinking processes over a more extended period to solve the problem are key features of the curriculum objectives assigned to this level. The operations include the central strategic thinking that is showing this level include are as follows: synthesizing, reflection, behavior, and management.

The limits of the study

Time limits

The study was conducted at the end of the first semester of 2015-2016.

Spatial limits

It is the central exam prepared by the Department of Evaluation and Examinations at the Ministry of Education in the United Arab Emirates.

Previous Studies

To the extent of the researcher's knowledge, no Arab or foreign studies were available to study the exam questions for the depth of knowledge, so the researcher chose some studies that mimic or close to the study's subject.

Mahmoud (2020) conducted a study to know the effect of using the Needham structural model in teaching science to develop the depth of scientific knowledge and high-ranking thinking skills and discover the relationship between them among students in middle school. Two research tools were prepared to achieve these goals: the depth of scientific knowledge test and the high-ranking thinking test. The research group consisted of (74) students, (37) students for the experimental group, and (37) students for the control group, from the students of the second year of middle school at Safaga Preparatory School for Girls, and a handbook has been prepared for the student, and a teacher's guide to guide him in teaching in light of Needham's construction model

in the first semester of the academic year 2019/2020, and the measurement tools were applied before and after the two groups, and the data was loaded, the results of the research indicated the following: The use of the Needham structural model strategy in science education had a significant impact on developing the depth of scientific knowledge, and high-rank thinking among second-grade middle school students, and the results indicated that there is a positive correlation relationship with statistical significance at the level (≥ 0.01) between levels of scientific knowledge depth and high-rank thinking among second-grade middle school students.

The study Kamaudin & Halim (2015) aimed to develop a chemistry curriculum based on the constructive five-stage model to help students overcome the alternate frameworks in the concept of illogical nature with the use of the ADDIE model and computer-aided instruction in designing the curriculum; the study sample consisted of (11) students as an experimental group. The results showed the combined Needham model's effectiveness with technology's effect in correcting the students' alternate frameworks related to the mall concept.

Al-Sayed's study (2018) aimed at identifying the effectiveness of using the fishbone strategy in teaching the unit "Transport in Living Organisms" for second-grade secondary students in developing the depth of biological knowledge and visual thinking skills. To achieve this goal, the "Transport in Living Organisms" unit, which was prescribed for second-grade secondary students in the biology course for the academic year 2016/2017, was reformulated and taught using the fishbone strategy. The research sample consisted of (64) students, and it was divided into two groups, one of them was control (32) students studied traditionally. The other was experimental (32) students studied using the fishbone strategy. Searching before and after, and the results were treated statistically using arithmetic means, standard deviation, and (T) test. The research found the effectiveness of using the fishbone strategy in developing both the depth of biological knowledge and the skills of visual thinking. In light of these results, the research presented a set of recommendations and suggested research.

Abu Rub Conducted a study in (2003) entitled "The impact of providing the seventh-grade students on their achievement of behavioral objectives textured mathematics in public schools in Jenin." The study was conducted on a sample of 64 students from seventh-grade students. The study showed differences in comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis, and evaluation among the students targeted in the behavioral objectives and student system compared to those who have not applied this to them this system. The result was in favor of those who applied the system mentioned above.

Moulton also conducted (Molton, 2003) a study of which one of its objectives was to identify the extent of the distribution of sample questions from tests on cognitive goals. (78) tests were analyzed in different courses. The study concluded that the questions focused on the minimum goals, and the study showed the lack of significant differences in the distribution of these questions, the proportion attributable to the variables: sex, specialization, and expertise.

In a similar study conducted by Nelson and Jane (Nielsen & Ginn, 2003) to ascertain the extent of applying the educational objectives by teachers in preparing the questions, the study sample consisted of the analysis of questions (114) teachers. It showed that 77% of the questions developed by teachers have focused on the goals of the levels of remembering, understanding, and applying.

Marceau and Paige (2002 Marso & Piggy) have summarized the results of a survey of (225) studies in different subjects in higher education. This study has shown several significant results, which included that these tests focus on remembering the level of cognitive goals.

Talbot's (2001) study aims to identify the level of cognitive goals prevailing in the teachers' tests in middle schools, where they were analyzed (65) test of educational and administrative tests in one of the colleges. The results showed that the most common objectives level of these tests is the level of knowledge and memory, followed by the application level.

Susana and others (2001, Susini, tall) conducted a study in which one of its goals was to ascertain the extent of the teachers' questions in the different exams to fit Bloom's Taxonomy. An analysis of (65) testing was done for this purpose. The study showed that the concentration of questions was on the lower levels of objectives.

Jaber Hamshary's study (2000) was conducted to analyze the final exams questions for some math courses at Al Quds Open University; The study found many and varied results. One of these results was that sample test questions did not include questions of higher-order thinking. Besides, these questions did not include levels of cognitive goals at all, but the majority of the questions were limited to questions from the application level.

Thacker's study (1998) was conducted to ascertain the extent of realizing the achievement exams' goals. The study aimed to determine whether the computer or the Internet questions were able to achieve behavioral and educational purposes. The study was conducted on a sample of (288) students and showed differences attributed to age, sex, and qualification variability.

Commenting on previous studies:

Through the review of the previous studies and their main components, many aspects of the agreement between these studies and some aspects of the differences can be monitored. And to observe these points, we take an analytical look at each of these studies.

The studies of Moulton (2003), Nielson & Ginn (2003), Mararso & Pigge (2002), Susini et al. (2001), Talbot (2001) agree that the exam questions focused on the lower levels of goals.

The study of Abu-Rub (2003) showed that there are differences in the process of assimilation, application, analysis, synthesis, and evaluation among students to whom the system of behavioral goals have been applied and students to whom this system haven't applied to them for the benefit of those who have been applied on them.

The study of Jabr and Al-Hashmari (2000) showed that the questions did not include all levels of cognitive goals but were limited to questions of application-level; the Thaker (1998) study showed differences due to the variable age, gender, and qualitatively of questions posed by computers or the Internet to achieve behavioral and educational goals.

The method and procedures

Study Approach:

The researcher used in this study the descriptive approach manner in an analytical style of the content to identify the depth of knowledge levels prevailing in the final examinations set by the Assessment and Examination Department of the Ministry of Education in the UAE and the light of variables: the form of questions (Pans/objective), and grade (sixth, seventh, VIII, IX, X, atheist ten) and subject matter (of Islamic education, Arabic language, English language, mathematics, science.

The study groups and their samples:

It is the study groups as well as the actual samples of all final exam questions for basic materials (Islamic Education, Arabic, English, mathematics, science) established by the Assessment Department at the Ministry of Education in the UAE for the first trimester of the academic year 2015/2016 of (30) exams. The subjects mentioned above are considered essential as a central test is being prepared at the ministry, starting from the sixth grade.

study tool:

To verify that the study's objective was accomplished, a particular form was designed to be used as a criterion for analyzing the exam questions. The researcher depended on the original Webform in preparing this form and on several experts in the Ministry of Education due to the lack of relevant studies. However, the study has been guided by educational goals and different levels (Zeitoun, 1997). The form was composed of the four-depth knowledge levels set by the Web in 1997 compared to a set of critical actions that describe them, and table (2) shows the components of the form.

Table 2: Components of the depth of knowledge levels

Depth cognitive levels content

Remembering and retrieval	mention, recognize, call, match, arrange, conduct, Quote, use, repeat, tabulate, define, identify
Concepts and skills	explain, compare, connect mentally, distinguish, demonstrate, summarize
Strategic thinking	Review, evaluate, argue, solve unusual problems, criticize, compare, explain the phenomenon, check, make judgments, presume, differentiate.
Thinking (enlarged)	extended Design, link, analyze, apply, invent, innovate, prove.

The validity of the tool

The tool was presented to a group of arbitrators who are specialists in the Ministry of Education to verify its validity. They were (9), where the average which didn't achieve high agreement up to 80% were excluded.

Reliability of the Tool

This tool's reliability has not been measured based on its contents simulated to Bloom's Taxonomy. The contents of the Bloom's Taxonomy have been monitored by specialized references (Zayton, 1997); Kitami, 1998); (Atkinson & Longman, 2003), where these references were unanimous stability rating, and a researcher considered it so acceptable for this study.

Statistical Treatment

SPSS statistically analyzed the results; the following statistical treatments were used: arithmetic averages, standard deviations, percentages, One-Way ANOVA analysis, (L S D) for Tele-comparisons, and T-test.

Results and discussion of the study

This section presents the results after the researcher collected the data using the study tool and presented them according to the study questions.

Results related to the first question

What is the most common depth of knowledge in the final exams for basic subjects (Islamic studies, Arabic language, English language, Math, and science) for grades (6th – 11th)?

To answer this question, an arithmetic averages percentage for each level of the 4th depth knowledge levels has been extracted, and numbers of the repeated exams contain each level of depth knowledge levels.

Table 3: Arithmetic averages of depth knowledge repeated levels for grades (6 – 11)

Class	Mental skills	Islamic study	Arabic language	English language	Math	Science
6th	Remembering	10.5	9.5	7.0	8.0	9.5
	Working with skill and concepts	4.5	5.0	5.5	5.5	7.0
	Strategically thinking	3.0	1.0	1.5	3.0	4.5
	Extended strategic thinking	0.0	0.0	0.5	1.0	0.5
7th	Remembering	9.5	11.5	7.0	7.0	7.5
	Working with skill and concepts	6.5	5.5	6.5	6.0	5.5
	Strategically thinking	5.0	1.5	2.0	4.5	3.5
	Extended strategic thinking	1.0	0.5	1.0	2.5	2.5
8th	Remembering	9.0	12.0	10.0	12.0	8.5
	Working with skill and concepts	7.0	4.5	8.0	7.0	6.5
	strategically thinking	4.5	1.0	1.5	3.5	5.5
	extended strategic thinking	0.5	0.0	1.0	2.0	2.0
9th	Remembering	11.5	13.0	16.5	9.5	14.5
	Working skills & concepts	8.0	8.0	9.5	4.5	7.0
	Strategically thinking	6.0	1.5	2.0	4.0	4.5
	extended strategic thinking	0.0	1.0	1.0	1.5	2.0
10th	Remembering	12.0	11.5	9.5	11.5	11.5
	Working skills & concepts	5.5	6.5	7.0	7.5	8.0
	Strategically thinking	5.0	2.0	2.5	5.5	3.5
	extended strategic thinking	2.5	1.5	1.5	3.0	3.0
11th	Remembering	11.0	12.0	12.0	10.5	9.5
	Working skills &	8.0	8.5	10.5	8.5	8.5

	concepts					
	Strategically thinking	7.0	2.0	2.5	4.5	6.0
	extended strategic thinking	2.0	2.0	1.5	2.0	3.5
Total	Remembering	10.6	11.6	10.3	9.8	10.2
	Working skills & concepts	6.6	6.3	7.8	6.5	7.1
	Strategically thinking	5.1	1.5	2.0	4.2	4.6
	extended strategic thinking	1.0	0.8	1.1	2.0	2.3

Table (3) shows that the most critical cognitive depth skills for all classes were memorizing materials (Arabic language, Islamic education, English language, science, mathematics), respectively, while the lowest cognitive depth skills were for extended thinking.

This explains that education is based on memorization rather than on higher thinking skills.

Results related to the second question:

Are there statically indicator differences at the level of indicator ($\alpha = 0.05$) among the known depth knowledge levels in final exams questions for the basic subjects (Islamic studies, Arabic language, English language, Math, and science) for grades (6th – 11th) variable attribute type of questions: essay & objective?

To answer this question, we have calculated the arithmetic averages and the standards deviations for each level of depth knowledge levels depending on the variable in question type. They were then compared using (T-test) for two independent samples, and the table (4) shows the associated results.

Table 4: T-test results (Differences in DOK's levels based on Question Type variable)

		Number	Average	Standard deviation	T	Indicator
Remember	objective	30	13.03	2.87	7.26	0.00
	essay	30	7.93	2.56		
Working with skill & concepts	objective	30	8.33	2.06	6.28	0.00
	essay	30	5.40	1.52		
Strategically thinking	objective	30	4.20	2.34	2.93	0.00
	essay	30	2.73	1.44		
Extended strategic thinking	objective	30	1.87	1.31	3.07	0.00
	essay	30	1.00	0.83		

It is evident from the table (4) that the statistical values (T) reached (7.26, 6.28, 2.93, 3.07) in the areas of depth knowledge (Remember, working with skill & concepts, strategically thinking, and extended strategic thinking), where all (T) values indicated it's statistically indicator. It showed that depth knowledge had been achieved with an objective exam with all dimensions compared to the essay questions with reviewing averages.

This explains that objective questions depend on identifying and guessing rather than retrieving information, making it easier for them to determine the correct answer.

Results related to the third question:

Are there any statistical indicator differences at the indicator level ($\alpha = 0.05$) among typical depth knowledge levels in final exams of basic subjects (Islamic studies, Arabic language, English language, Math, and science) for the grades (6th – 11th) attributable to the variable subject?

To answer this question, we have calculated the arithmetic averages and the standards deviations for each level of depth knowledge levels depending on the subject type changes. Then they were compared through the use of variance and test definitive comparisons analysis test, and the table (5) shows the associated results.

Table 5: Arithmetic averages and standards deviation of depth knowledge dimensions depending on the variable subject

Depthknowledge level	subject	number	average	Standard deviation
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Remember	Islamic studies	12	10.58	5.11
	Arabic language	12	11.58	3.03
	English language	12	10.33	4.58
	Math	12	9.75	3.14
	Science	12	10.17	2.52
	Total	60	10.48	3.73
Working with skills and concepts	Islamic studies	12	6.58	2.35
	Arabic language	12	6.33	2.74
	English language	12	7.83	2.25
	Math	12	6.50	2.35
	Science	12	7.08	1.93
	Total	60	6.87	2.33
Strategically thinking	Islamic studies	12	5.08	2.71
	Arabic language	12	1.50	0.80
	English language	12	2.00	0.74
	Math	12	4.17	1.11
	Science	12	4.58	1.31
	Total	60	3.47	2.06
Extended strategic thinking	Islamic studies	12	1.00	1.21
	Arabic language	12	0.83	1.03
	English language	12	1.08	0.67
	Math	12	2.00	0.95
	Science	12	2.25	1.29
	Total	60	1.43	1.17

You can see from the table(5) that there are apparent differences in in-depth knowledge dimensions (Remember, working with skills & concepts, strategically thinking, and extended strategic thinking) depending on the variable subject type, and to verify that these differences are essential. A statistical indicator, variance analysis, was done with associated results in table (6).

Table 6: Results of variance analysis of depth knowledge differences depending on subject variability

		Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Average squares	F	Indicator
Remember	Among groups	22.6	4	5.6	0.4	0.8
	Inside groups	796.4	55	14.5		
	total	819.0	59			
working with skill & concepts	Among groups	17.8	4	4.4	0.8	0.5
	Inside groups	301.2	55	5.5		
	total	318.9	59			
strategically thinking	Among groups	124.4	4	31.1	13.5	0.0
	Inside groups	126.5	55	2.3		
	total	250.9	59			
extended strategic thinking	Among groups	19.9	4	5.0	4.5	0.0
	Inside groups	60.8	55	1.1		
	total	80.7	59			

The statistical value (F) reached (0.40, 0.80, 13.5, & 4.5) of depth knowledge areas (Remember, working with skill & concepts, strategically thinking, and extended strategic thinking) where the differences indicated the strategic thinking and the comprehensive strategic thinking only. To determine which of the

subjects the indicator differences lie, a satisfactory comparison test was conducted with the associated results in a table (7).

Table 7: Satisfactory results of post comparison depending on subject variability

		Islamic studies	Arabic language	English language	Math	Science
strategically thinking	Islamic studies		3.583*	3.083*	0.92	0.50
	Arabic language			-0.50	-2.667-*	-3.083-*
	English language				-2.167-*	-2.583-*
	Math					-0.42
	Science					
extended strategic thinking	Islamic studies	0.17		-0.08	-1.000-*	-1.250-*
	Arabic language			-0.25	-1.167-*	-1.417-*
	English language				-.917-*	-1.167-*
	Math					-0.25
	Science					

We can see from table (7) that in strategic thinking, the differences were evident between Islamic studies from one hand and Arabic, English languages where the differences favor Islamic studies. Also, the indicator difference between Math, on the one hand, and Arabic, English languages, on the other hand, was in favor of Math, as for the indicator difference between science and Arabic, English was also in favor of Science. When it comes to extended strategic thinking, we can see that the indicator differences between Math on one hand & Islamic studies, Arabic & English languages on the other, were in favor of Math, and it was in favor of Science against Arabic, English languages, and Islamic studies.

Results related to the fourth question:

Are there any statistical indicator differences at the indicator level ($\alpha=0.05$) between expected depth knowledge levels in final exams of basic subjects (Islamic studies, Arabic language, English language, Math, and Science) for grades (6th – 11th) depending on classroom-type?

We have calculated the arithmetic averages and standard deviations for each level of depth knowledge levels depending on classroom-type changes to answer this question. Then they were compared through the use of variance and test definitive comparisons analysis test. Table (8) shows the associated results.

Table 8: Arithmetic averages and standards deviation of depth knowledge dimensions depending on variable classroom

	Grade	number	average	Standard deviation
Remember	6 th grade	10	8.9	4.4
	7 th grade	10	8.5	2.7
	8 th grade	10	10.3	3.5
	9 th grade	10	13.0	3.8
	10 th grade	10	11.2	3.5
	11 th grade	10	11.0	3.2
	total	60	10.5	3.7
Working skill ad concepts	6 th grade	10	5.5	2.2

	7 th grade	10	6.0	0.9
	8 th grade	10	6.6	2.5
	9 th grade	10	7.4	2.8
	10 th grade	10	6.9	1.4
	11 th grade	10	8.8	2.4
	total	60	6.9	2.3
Strategically thinking	6 th grade	10	2.6	1.5
	7 th grade	10	3.3	1.8
	8 th grade	10	3.2	2.5
	9 th grade	10	3.6	2.5
	10 th grade	10	3.7	1.6
	11 th grade	10	4.4	2.3
	total	60	3.5	2.1
Extended strategic thinking	6 th grade	10	0.4	0.5
	7 th grade	10	1.5	1.1
	8 th grade	10	1.1	1.1
	9 th grade	10	1.1	0.9
	10 th grade	10	2.3	1.1
	11 th grade	10	2.2	1.2
	total	60	1.4	1.2

We can see from table (8) that there are essential differences in in-depth knowledge dimensions (Remember, working with skill & concepts, strategically thinking, and extended strategic thinking) depending on classroom variability. To verify that these differences have statistical indicators, we have done an analyst test with associated results in table (9).

Table 9: Results of analyst variation of depth knowledge differences depending on classroom variability

		Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Average squares	F	Indicator
Remember	Among groups	135.9	5	27.2	2.1	0.1
	Inside groups	683.1	54	12.7		
	total	819.0	59			
working with skill & concepts	Among groups	67.1	5	13.4	2.9	0.0
	Inside groups	251.8	54	4.7		
	total	318.9	59			
strategically thinking	Among groups	17.9	5	3.6	0.8	0.5
	Inside groups	233.0	54	4.3		

	total	250.9	59			
extended strategic thinking^a	Among groups	26.3	5	5.3	5.2	0.0
	Inside groups	54.4	54	1.0		
	total	80.7	59			

We can see from table (9) that indicator values of (F) reached (2.10, 2.90, 0.80, 5.20) in-depth knowledge areas (Remember, working with skill & concepts, strategically thinking, and extended strategic thinking) where the indicators differences were in working with skill & concepts and extended strategic thinking only. And to determine which subject the indicator differences fall, a posterior comparison test was done with associated results in table (10).

Table 10: Satisfactory results of comparison posterior depending on classroom variability

		6 th grade	7 th grade	8 th grade	9 th grade	10 th grade	11 th grade
working with skill & concepts	6 th grade		-0.50	-1.10	-1.90	-1.40	-3.30*
	7 th grade			-0.60	-1.40	-0.90	-2.80*
	8 th grade				-0.80	-0.30	-2.20*
	9 th grade					0.50	-1.40
	10 th grade						-1.90
extended strategic thinking	11 th grade						
	6 th grade		-1.10*	-0.70	-0.70	-1.90*	-1.80*
	7 th grade			0.40	0.40	-0.80	-0.70
	8 th grade				0.00	-1.20*	-1.10*
	9 th grade					-1.20*	-1.10*
	10 th grade						0.10
	11 th grade						

We can see from table (10) that the differences in working skills and concepts were between (6th grade, 7th& 8th) on the one hand and with 11th grade, on the other hand, where the differences were in favor of 11th grade. Also, the differences in extended strategic thinking between (6th, 8th& 9th) on the one hand and the 11th, on the other hand, were in favor of the 11th grade.

This is explained by the temporal age where 11th-grade students can practice extended thinking more than lower-class students.

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